

Deliverable D9.5

DISSEMINATION AND COMMUNICATION MATERIALS (2 | 3)

Deliverable report

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Disclaimer

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DIGIECOQUARRY project is fully concerned about the potential social risks that may arise as consequence of project's activities. For this reason, a dedicated Work Package (WP7 - Mechanisms for social acceptance & interaction with policy makers) is active since the beginning of the project identifying, analysing and monitoring social risks in each of the project sites. Main social risks have been already analysed and classified in deliverables 7.1 and 7.2, including also potential risks of DIGIECOQUARRY technologies' deployment beyond the end of the project. The identification and classification of social risks allows a close follow up of main potential negative impacts in society to avoid them along the whole project activities. Among potential social risks, impact in the workforce is monitored with specific attention to ensure full adaptation of workers to new working technologies and processes and avoid job destruction.

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List of Abbreviations

ABBREVIATION	DESCRIPTION
DEQ	DIGIECOQUARRY
D	Deliverable
DCEP	Dissemination, Communication and Exploitation Plan
D&C	Dissemination and Communication
GA	Grant Agreement
EURMKB	European Union Raw Materials Knowledge Base
H2020	Horizon 2020
ICT	Information and communications technology
IQS	Intelligent Quarrying System
OEM	Information and communications technology
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
RM	Raw Materials
RMIS	Raw Materials Information System
SLO	Social License to Operate
WP	Work Package

1 Executive Summary

This report, titled 'D9.5: Dissemination and communication materials (2|3)', aims to display all DIGIECOQUARRY's marketing items that have been produced between June 2022 and May 2023.

DIGIECOQUARRY is a Horizon 2020 project that aims to design, develop and validate in 5 pilot environments an Innovative Quarrying System (IQS) comprising sensors, processes, tools and methods for data capture, processing and sharing to provide integrated, digitalised, automatic and real-time process control for aggregates quarries.

The DIGIECOQUARRY consortium will combine the latest researched and advanced technologies applied to quarry operations together with the integration of selected innovative digital solutions to boost the capacity of the aggregates sector, enhance health and safety conditions for workers, improve the selectivity and efficiency of the aggregates sites, maximise sustainability and resource efficiency in quarry operations and foster social acceptance of the extractive industry.

Figure 1. DIGIECOQUARRY's concept.

2 Introduction

Work Package 9: Implementation of the dissemination, communication and exploitation strategy seeks to design, execute, monitor and evaluate all the activities related to dissemination and communication carried within the framework of DIGIECOQUARRY. It considers specific actions and establishes the beneficiaries' responsibilities to ensure the project and its results are widely broadcasted and reach the target audience.

On the other hand, this WP also will define a knowledge management strategy according to the background of each partner, the ownership of the foreground identified and the exploitation agreements among the parties.

With the above-stated considered, WP9 outlines (see Figure 2):

- What has been disseminated. Devoting to the basic project-related information delivered throughout the project.
- To whom the project has been disseminated. Consisting of the key stakeholder groups that will be the main audience for the project's public campaign.
- How the project has been disseminated. Including all the channels and tools that will be used by project partners to successfully implement the activities.
- When the project has been disseminated. Providing guidelines to ensure that the timing of the actions is appropriate during the lifespan of the project and beyond.
- Monitoring of the process. Managing the indicators to gauge success on the dissemination, awareness raising and communication actions, enabling partners to refine efforts over the course of the project.

Figure 2. DCEP strategy.

2.1 Relation to other activities and deliverables

Dissemination, Communication and Exploitation strategies and actions are the cornerstones for generating a deep impact on DEQ's results when attracting the interest of the main stakeholders and social acceptance.

To maximise the impact beyond the project lifetime, these actions will be undertaken within three WPs: WP7. Mechanisms for social acceptance and interaction with policymakers; WP8. Clustering activities for a solid EU knowledge base on RM; and WP9. Dissemination, Communication and Exploitation.

These three WPs will closely work during the 48 months the project lasts. Coordination meetings are regularly held to monitor the results achieved within the social, clustering, dissemination, communication and exploitation actions.

Figure 3. Relationship between WPs.

2.2 Partners' role in the dissemination strategy

DIGIECOQUARRY partners, due to their strategic positioning in Europe (and also ASOGRAVAS and MINTEK in Colombia and South Africa, respectively), count with vast capacities to influence the target communities and will act as multipliers. *Table 1* summarises the main dissemination strategies to be implemented:

Table 1. Dissemination Strategy per partner profile.

PARTNERS	DISSEMINATION STRATEGY
Large companies: SANDVIK, METSO, MAXAM, AKKA	They have an important influence and impact in the aggregates industry, quarry technology providers, construction and complementary sectors (such as OEMs and 1 st tier providers) including their client networks and commercialisation channels. Dissemination will focus on engaging potential customers interested in exploiting product/services generated.
SMEs: ITK, ARCO, MAESTRO, DH&P, ABAUT, APP, SIGMA, ZABALA	They are mainly interested in attracting new clients and reinforcing the loyalty of customer portfolio thanks to the newly acquired competitive advantages related to the KTAs and the IQS. SMEs will make available to DIGIECOQUARRY their existing client/supplier networks as well as the involvement of their Marketing and Communication departments.
Quarries: VICAT, HANSON, HOLCIM, CSI, CIMPOR	They are eager to extend their client portfolio and strengthen links with the already existing ones. Their Dissemination actions will be based on the presentation of improved products (in quality, economic, environmental and social terms) to engage specific stakeholders and end users, mainly in the construction sector (e.g., cement, road base and subbase, mortar, asphalt, etc). Also, they would like to influence positively the perception of quarrying in the society (see section 2.3).
R&D and Academia: MUL, CHALMERS, UPM, MINTEK, ROCTIM	They aim at engaging with the EU (and also international) scientific and industrial communities to raise awareness about the project and contribute to knowledge generation and sharing. They pursue the generation of new research lines and training programmes aligned with the key pillars established in H2020. They are seeking to involve their research groups and communication departments in dissemination activities. Reinforcement of the EU RM' sector.

<p>International cooperation, Promoters & Public bodies: ANEFA, DGASTUR, ASOGRAVAS</p>	<p>They will engage with their network of contacts to maximise their dissemination impact by using their wide partners network, benefiting from their experience/expertise in meetings, workshops and conferences to establish contact and build relations with target groups of the wide range of themes of DIGIECOQUARRY. They would like to bridge the gap between science, practice and society by organising targeted stakeholder workshops to bring together stakeholders, industry, policy makers and citizens to facilitate public acceptance.</p>
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2.3 Scope of the deliverable

This report, titled ‘D9.5: Dissemination and communication materials (2|3)’, aims to showcase all marketing materials that have been produced during the last 12 months to maximise the project’s visibility and impact, which translates into:

- Effective promotion of the project and its results to all target groups and audiences, both at national and European levels.
- Establishment of links and liaisons with international organisations and other interested stakeholders.
- Creating synergies with other relevant projects and initiatives.
- Project outcomes validation to obtain feedback from expert groups, scientists and interested user communities.

2.4 Structure of the deliverable

With the above in mind, the “Report on Dissemination and Communication Activities” is structured as follows:

Section 1 – Executive summary. Contains a brief fact sheet about the project.

Section 2 – Introduction. Provides meaningful information regarding the DCEP and its structure as well as its scope and its relation to other tasks, activities and deliverables.

Section 3 – Dissemination assets.

Section 4 – Target groups.

Section 5 – Dissemination and communication materials.

Section 6 – Conclusions: Summarises the conclusions of this report as well as the next planned reviews of this document.

Annex I

3 Dissemination Assets

The Project's assets and outcomes that are here described, have been disseminated by all partners with a view to maximise the project's impact and visibility. This information is being conveyed in a meaningful way and tailored to each stakeholder group, in order to promote not only the DIGIECOQUARRY's results, but also its vision and aim.

- The **conceptual aspects** of the project, meaning the whole project concept, its innovative characteristics, its impact both on business and at social level, etc.
- The **technical achievements of the project** like the DIGIECOQUARRY IQS platform and the respective ICT infrastructure and needed toolkits. The assets of this category will be highly disseminated on appropriate channels once these tools are developed and thus a more detailed communication strategy will be contained in the next version of the DCEP.
- The **scientific knowledge** that derives from the project in the form of reports, scientific articles, etc.
- All the spectrum of the **project's activities**, like the four workshops that will be organized in the framework of DIGIECOQUARRY, the closing event, the participation in external events and every other action that could be of interest to the project's target groups.

Figure 4. DIGIECOQUARRY's dissemination assets

4 Target groups

The key stakeholders of DIGIECOQUARRY can be segmented into the four target groups outlined below. The actual stakeholders have been identified and registered in an internal stakeholders' Excel worksheet.

- **Business stakeholders:** with potential interest in the project's successful execution and results that will expand the project's scope towards new market opportunities to maximise its impact.
- **Academic and research stakeholders:** Academics, researchers and experts focused on advancing the scientific fields cross-cutting DIGIECOQUARRY.
- **Governmental and policy stakeholders:** policy makers are of primary interest for the consortium given that they are responsible for setting the guidelines of the current and future mining policies that will affect the commercial feasibility of DIGIECOQUARRY.
- **General public stakeholders:** non-governmental organizations, civil society groups or simply citizens, interested in the potential of DIGIECOQUARRY to address needs relevant to them.

Figure 5. DIGIECOQUARRY's stakeholders.

Table 2. Target audiences, aims and key messages.

TARGET AUDIENCE	AIM	KEY MESSAGES
1. Aggregates industries & Quarries / RM Stakeholders and end users Material providers Industry associations and representatives	Final users of DIGIECOQUARRY's result Commercial exploitation Project involvement Clustering via WP8	Main results and experience from pilots Improved performance, H&S, social and environmental indicators Economic, investment & cost analysis Prospects of prolonging the productive life cycles of quarries
2. ICT industry Technology providers Associations and representatives	New range of services in the quarry sector Commercial exploitation Open and flexible methodologies for interoperability of ICT tools	Main results and experience reports from the pilots Available materials/services and knowledge generated
3. Researchers at universities, R&D centres or and Scientific societies in RM	Enhanced scientific knowledge R&D cooperation and promotion Clustering via WP8	Increase data available for research Main results shared in EURMKB and RMIS
4. Construction sector and other clients	Promote the development of new or improved products and services based on DIGIECOQUARRY results	Improved cost-efficient products, H&S, social & environmental KPIs Raise awareness
5. Citizens and civil society	General awareness Social License to Operate (SLO) Project involvement via WP7	Community Engagement Strategies Social Awareness plan Local engagement plan
6. Policy makers and funding bodies (Government, Regulatory agencies) at local, national and EU level	Provide strong evidence to establish new policies, initiatives and roadmaps for RM Interaction in WP7	Reinforcement of the Quarrying sector Improved performance, H&S, social and environmental indicators Raise awareness
7. Media, journalists and other groups at European level (e.g., environment, energy, safety, NGOs, Consumer's organisations...)	General awareness Improved perception of the extractive industry Trend setters	Improved performance, H&S, social and environmental indicators Available materials/services for communication purposes

A preliminary list of identified stakeholders is included in Annex I of D9.1: Dissemination, Communication and Exploitation Plan.

5 Dissemination and Communication materials

5.1 Custom roll-ups

A joint roll up was designed for APP Consultoría de proyectos and ANEFA for BIMExpo. More about this event can be found in *D9.6: Report on dissemination and communication activities*.

Figure 6. Roll-up for APP and ANEFA.

A custom made roll up was designed for Dohmen, Herzog and Partner, one of our partners, for ForumMiro. More about this event can be found in *D9.6: Report on dissemination and communication activities*.

Figure 7. Roll up for DH&P.

5.2 Flyers

A single, unfolded printed sheet that is used to draw attention to the project at events was produced. It contains a very simple message about the project that can be conveyed quickly.

Figure 8. DEQ flyers

5.3 Infographics

The D&C team has designed five infographics which show the technologies that will be implemented in each pilot site.

Figure 9. Infographic: technologies to be implemented in Valdilecha.

Figure 10. Infographic: technologies to be implemented in Alenquer.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 101003750

Figure 11. Infographic: technologies to be implemented in Fenouillet.

Figure 12. Infographic: technologies to be implemented in Mammendorf.

Figure 13. Infographic: technologies to be implemented in Pioltello.

5.4 Videos

During this last period, DIGIECOQUARRY has been releasing the following videos:

- DEQ spot: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=8Ca24To3iGg>
- WP leaders visit Valdilecha quarry during the First Review Meeting: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=-iPSrg5gpEg>
- A series of interviews to WP leaders is in the making, but the first one can be found here: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=fbLiWJ5RSgY&t=169s>

Also, ASOGRAVAS, our Colombian partner, has posted on their YouTube channel some videos disseminating DEQ:

- <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=8vuJzRZ8yQU>
- <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=RQM5IRr14mY>

5.5 Online presence

5.5.1 Website

The website is the main communication and dissemination tool of the project. Thus, it is continuously fed with news and contents about the project: <https://digiecoquarry.eu/>

Since its launch and as of today, the website is being monitored and actions are being taken to reach the targets for traffic, reach, etc. Below some of the statistics are shown:

- Users: 737
- Average interaction time: 2 min 29 s
- The country from where the website has been more visited is Spain, followed by Germany, Italy, France, Portugal, Austria and Sweden.

Figure 14. Web statistics.

More information about DEQ's website can be found in *D9.2: DIGIECOQUARRY's website*.

5.5.2 Social Media

Keeping DEQ's social media profiles updated is key to attract the public's interest, feedback and build relationships. On the other hand, it helps DEQ's D&C team to engage with the audience and find out what people are saying about the project.

Due to this, DEQ's LinkedIn, Twitter, Instagram, Facebook, YouTube, and Vimeo profiles are frequently updated with posts related to a wide variety of topics, ranging from the project itself to raw materials related contents, EU news, etc.

DIGIECOQUARRY's social media profiles are:

LinkedIn: <https://www.linkedin.com/company/digiecoquarry>

Instagram: <https://www.instagram.com/digiecoquarry/>

Twitter: https://twitter.com/digi_eco

Facebook: <https://www.facebook.com/Digiecoquarry>

YouTube: <https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCdxXOCOK6kY5YEiW-sw1McA>

Vimeo: <https://vimeo.com/digiecoquarry>

6 Conclusions

This document, titled “Report on Dissemination and Communication Activities”, describes the marketing materials that have been produced between months 13 to 24 to help the dissemination of the DIGIECOQUARRY project in different congresses, fairs, and presentations.

As the project evolves, this document will be updated in month 36.

7 References

The following references have been used for the preparation of this deliverable:

- DIGIECOQUARRY Grant Agreement number 101003750.
- D9.1: Dissemination, Communication and Exploitation Plan (DCEP).

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10 Annex I. Other released materials

Since the very beginning of the project, several materials have been designed and printed. They can be found in D9.3 Dissemination and Communication materials (1|3), but a slight recap is also shown below.

Figure 15. Quarrying process infographic.

Figure 16. Leaflet print version.

Figure 17. Online leaflet

